

CARE Comm (Climate Action Renewable Energy Communication)

You are invited to participate in a research study titled **C.A.R.E. Comm** (Climate Action Renewable Energy Communication Reference: PP2024_30) led by Daniel Wuebben and the Communication, Impact, and Social Transformation research group from the Universidad Pontificia Comillas in Madrid, Spain. The survey will consist of 26 questions, some with multiple responses and others that ask you to enter text. It should take around 20 minutes to complete. Topics include:

1. **Climate Awareness:** Facts, personal and institutional actions, and mitigation strategies.
2. **Psychology and Spirituality:** Human behavior, eco-anxiety, spiritual beliefs, and future perceptions.
3. **Energy Literacy:** Knowledge of global decarbonization efforts and local energy consumption metrics.
4. **Branding and Sustainability:** Awareness of sustainable brands and their real-world impacts.

Your participation in this survey is entirely voluntary, and there are no known risks associated with it. There will be no cost or compensation for participating. Your participation will help us gather valuable data to better understand how young people from across Europe, North America and South America engage with the global issue of climate change and renewable energy.

Confidentiality and Data Handling

All of your responses will remain anonymous and confidential. Your answers will be associated with a unique code rather than your name, and no personal information will be shared publicly. Any data gathered will be securely stored per current data protection laws and will only be accessed by research team members for this project. If the aggregated data is published, no individual information will be disclosed. Your participation is confidential. All information gathered will be stored securely and will only be accessed by the research team. If you choose to provide a personal identifier (e.g., a self-generated code), it will be used only for tracking purposes and will not compromise your anonymity. Should you decide to withdraw from the study at any point, any stored data related to your participation will be deleted immediately. All recordings and data will be destroyed after five years.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation is voluntary, and by continuing with the survey, you are providing your consent to participate. You may withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequences. If you wish to withdraw after completing the survey, you may contact the researcher, and your data will be erased from the project records.

If you have any questions regarding this research or your participation, please contact the principal investigator, **Daniel Wuebben**, at dlewis@comillas.edu

Thank you for your time and valuable contribution to this study.

Demographic Information

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To ensure your responses remain anonymous while allowing us to identify your submission for any follow-up, please create a personal code using the following format:

Take the **first letter of your first name**.

- For example, if your name is Sarah, the first letter is "S."

Combine this with the **two digits of the day and two digits of the month you were born**.

- For example, if your birthday is August 5th, your digits would be "0508."
- Do **NOT include** the year you were born.

Example:

- If your name is Sarah and your birthday is August 5th, your code will be **S0508** and if your name is Tom and you were born 19 April your code will be **T1904**.

Your final code will be **unique one letter followed by four digits** (e.g. x1234)

Please enter **your** one digit four letter code below. This code will help us track your responses without compromising your privacy.

Again, your first digits are the day of the month you were born (0 to 31) and the month:

January = 01
February = 02
March = 03
April = 04
May = 05
June = 06
July = 07
August = 08
September = 09
October = 10
November = 11
December = 12

*

Escriba al menos 5 caracteres

2

What is your current age? *

El valor debe ser un número.

3

Name of school, current year of study, and major? *

4

What is your gender?

- Woman
- Man
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say
- Gender queer/Gender fluid

5

In what type of environment have you lived mainly?

- Urban (within a city limit)
- Suburban (near a city)
- Rural (A good distance from a city)
- Otras

6

How would you describe your family's social class (e.g. wealth, influence, and status)?

- Lower middle class
- Middle class
- Upper middle class
- Upper upper class

Beliefs and Perceptions about Climate Change

7

Human activities are a major cause of climate change *

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree
- Neutral

8

My local environment WILL BE negatively influenced by climate change *

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

9

When do you think climate change will start to harm PEOPLE where you live? *

- They are being harmed now
- In approximately 5 years (~2030)
- In approximately 15 years (~2040)
- In approximately 25 years (~2050)
- Never

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To understand your general level of awareness about climate change, **how often do you think about climate change? ***

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Never or almost never

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Human activities are **NOT** a major cause of climate change *

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree
- Neutral

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To what extent do you feel a **personal responsibility to reduce climate change?**

1= Not at all personally responsible
10= Completely responsible

*

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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13

Do you think it is likely that **limiting your energy use** would **help reduce climate change?**

1 = Not at all likely to reduce
10 = Extremely likely to reduce

*

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

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Now imagine that **large numbers of people limit their energy use**. How likely do you think it is that this **would reduce climate change?**

1 = Not at all likely to reduce
10 = Extremely likely to reduce *

*

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

15

To what extent are you in favor or against **increasing taxes on fossil fuels, such as oil, gas, and coal?** *

*

- Strongly against
- Somewhat against
- Somewhat in favor
- Strongly in favor
- Don't know

Perceived Impact of Climate Policies

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To what extent are you in favor or against using **public money to subsidize (or further subsidize) the following climate actions**

	Strongly Against	Somewhat Against	Somewhat in Favor	Strongly in Favor	Id
Large scale wind farms or solar fields	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Home solar (e.g. rooftop solar panels)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Green hydrogen	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Retrofitting older buildings	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Purchase of electric vehicles for personal use	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Promoting plant-based diets	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

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If your country introduces policies to reduce climate change, how likely is it that **these policies will improve people's health?**

1= Not at all likely
10= Extremely likely

*

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

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If your country introduces policies to reduce climate change, how likely is it that **these policies will reduce employment and harm the economy?**

1= Not at all likely
10= Extremely likely

*

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

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Can you **name any international public organizations, religious organizations, national governments, or private corporations** that stand out for their efforts to enact **sustainable practices?** Please list as many as you can think of *

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What are the **main reasons** you believe the **organizations and companies you listed are sustainable?** (Select all that apply) *

- Commitment to reducing carbon emissions
- Use of renewable energy sources
- Sustainable supply chain practices
- Ethical sourcing of materials
- Strong corporate social responsibility (CSR) programs
- Transparency and reporting on environmental impact
- Innovative sustainable products or services
- Environmental certifications (e.g., LEED, Fair Trade)
- Reduction of waste and recycling initiatives
- Long-term sustainability goals and progress
- Otras

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Please rank the following sectors in terms of their overall sustainability, with 1 being the most sustainable and 6 being the least sustainable *

Beauty (Cosmetics, lotions, perfumes, etc.)

Technology (laptops, cellular phones etc.)

Cars

Processed foods

Sportswear (Shoes, jerseys, etc.)

Energy

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Please write the names of any companies in these sectors that come to mind when you think of sustainability efforts.

You can signal the group with a letter (e.g. T- Sony, Helium, C- Ferrari, Ford.)

Technology Company (T)

Car Company (C)

Sportswear Company (S)

Energy Company (E)

Food Company (F)

Beauty (B)

Awareness and Engagement with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

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The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a collection of 17 global goals designed to address pressing challenges such as poverty, inequality, climate change, environmental degradation, peace, and justice. These goals are intended to create a more sustainable and equitable world by 2030.

On a scale of 1 to 5, how familiar and engaged are you with the SDGs?

*

- 1 - I have never heard of the SDGs.
- 2 - I have heard of the SDGs, but I am not familiar with them.
- 3 - I have some basic understanding of the SDGs.
- 4 - I have basic understanding of the SDGs have directly engaged with the SDGs in course work and/or projects inside or outside school.
- 5 - I have advanced knowledge of the SDGs and my course work and/or projects engage directly with the SDGs on at least a monthly basis.

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Please rank the following Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in order of their importance to you, with 1 being the most important and 8 being the least important.

*

SDG 13: Climate Action (Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts)

SDG 4: Quality Education (Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all)

SDG 2: Zero Hunger (End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture)

SDG 16: Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions (Promote peaceful and inclusive societies, provide access to justice for all, and build effective, accountable institutions at all levels)

SDG 3: Good Health and Well-being (Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages)

SDG 1: No Poverty (End poverty in all its forms everywhere)

SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth (Promote sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all)

SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation (Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all)

Engagement and Spirituality

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To what extent do you think that the following groups are responsible for reducing climate change?

	Not at all responsible	Somewhat responsible	Partially Responsible	Fully Responsible	Id
Governments	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Corporations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Religious Organizations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
NGOs (Greenpeace, Clean Air Task Force)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Intergovernmental Organizations (United Nations, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), Clean Energy Ministerial, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	
Wealthy Nations such as the G8 (Germany, UK, Japan, USA, China, Italy, Canada, France)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

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Spirituality and religious education have a significant impact on climate change

- Strongly Disagree
- Somewhat Agree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Somewhat Agree
- Strongly Agree
- Otras

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Do you participate in the following environmental or climate related actions?

	Never	Sometimes/Occasionally	Frequently/Often	Almost
Recycle household waste, e.g. paper, plastic, aluminum, glass	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Post or share climate and environment-related content on social media	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Eliminate single-use plastic whenever possible	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Minimize electricity consumption by turning off unneeded lights, keep the thermostat set lower in winter and higher in summer, use ceiling fans, etc.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Talk to family, friends, or coworkers about climate change	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Eat a low-carbon, plant based diet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Engage in a climate workshops, marches, or protests	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Choose low-emissions travel mode even if it costs a little bit more or takes more time (e.g. traveling by train instead of flight)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Buy less clothes or consciously choose second-hand clothing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Participate in a spiritual practice (e.g. meditate, mass, prayer) or event related to climate or environment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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Is there anything else you would like to share with the research team?

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